

**OF MYASTHENIA GRAVIS AND EVALUATION OF ITS INFLUENCE
ON THE COURSE OF THE DISEASE**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7563627>

ABSTRACT. Myasthenia gravis is characterized by weakness and rapid fatigue of any of the muscles under your voluntary control. It is caused by a disturbance in the normal communication between the nerves and the muscles. There is no cure for myasthenia gravis, but treatment can help relieve signs and symptoms, such as weakness in the arms or legs, double vision, drooping eyelids and difficulty speaking, chewing, swallowing and breathing. Although the condition can affect people of any age, it is more common in women under 40 and in men over 60.

Keywords: myasthenia gravis, neuropsychological condition, muscle weakness, acetylcholine receptors

Introduction. Myasthenia gravis is caused by impaired transmission of nerve impulses to the muscles. It occurs when the normal connection between nerve and muscle is interrupted at the nerve-muscle junction, the place where nerve cells connect to the muscles they control. In myasthenia gravis, antibodies (immune proteins produced by the body's immune system) block, alter or destroy acetylcholine receptors at the neuromuscular synapse, which prevents muscle contraction. This is most often caused by antibodies to the acetylcholine receptor itself, but antibodies to other proteins, such as the muscle-specific kinase protein), can also disrupt transmission at the neuromuscular junction. Myasthenia gravis affects both men and women and occurs in all racial and ethnic groups. It most often affects young adult women (under age 40) and older men (over age 60), but can occur at any age, including childhood. Myasthenia gravis is not hereditary and is not contagious. Sometimes the condition can occur in more than one member of the same family. Although myasthenia gravis rarely occurs in infants, a fetus can get antibodies from a mother with myasthenia gravis, a condition called neonatal myasthenia gravis. Neonatal myasthenia gravis is usually temporary, and the baby's symptoms usually disappear within two to three months after birth. In rare cases, children of a healthy mother may develop congenital myasthenia gravis. This is not an autoimmune disease, but is caused by defective genes that produce abnormal

proteins in the neuromuscular junction and can cause myasthenia gravis-like symptoms.

Diagnostic imaging. Diagnostic chest imaging using computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) can reveal the presence of a thymoma.

Conclusions: With treatment, most people with myasthenia gravis can significantly reduce muscle weakness and lead normal or nearly normal lives. In some cases of myasthenia gravis, remission - temporary or permanent - may occur and muscle weakness may disappear completely, so that medication can be discontinued. Stable, long-term complete remissions are the goal of thymectomy and may occur in about 50 percent of people who have undergone the procedure.

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